

Preventive Effect of Pretreatment with Intravenous Metoclopramide on Incidence of Post Laparoscopic Surgery Nausea and Vomiting

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Abstract

Introduction: Common complications following anesthesia include Postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV), which leads to patient dissatisfaction and discomfort. The incidence of PONV after inhalational general anesthesia is up to 30% [1]. When anesthetics are used with no prophylaxis, and in certain high-risk patients, the incidence of PONV can reach up to 70% [2]. Furthermore, laparoscopic surgeries are associated with an even higher incidence of PONV (40%-75%) [3]. This makes PONV one of the most prevalent post-operational complaints [4].

Methods: This case control study includes 79 patients with high PONV risk scores scheduled for laparoscopic cholecystectomy under general anesthesia in Duhok hospitals. 40 patients received 8 mg (2ml) metoclopramide intravenously as pretreatment, while 39 patients received normal saline (2ml) as the control group. After 48 hours, we called patients and asked them about the incidence and severity of PONV.

Result: statically insignificant differences in the incidence of PONV between both groups (p-value 0.91). The incidence of PONV in this study was (27.8%) which correlates with the PONV risk score mean (2.48) and was statistically significant with a p-value of less than 0.01 and a 95% confidence score (2.13, 18.32).

Conclusion: PONV risk score is effective in the prediction of the incidence of PONV, and Metoclopramide is ineffective as a single drug in the prevention of PONV in high-risk patients.

Introduction

Background

Postoperative Nausea and Vomiting (PONV) is a common complication following anesthesia, which

leads to patient dissatisfaction and discomfort [4]. General anesthesia has been considered to be a greater cause of PONV in terms of both frequency and severity when compared with regional anesthetic techniques

More Information

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for a very long time [5]. The incidence of PONV after inhalational general anesthesia is up to 30% [1]. When anesthetics are used with no prophylaxis, and in certain high-risk patients, the incidence of PONV can reach up to 70% [2]. Furthermore, laparoscopic surgeries are associated with an even higher incidence of PONV (40%-75%) [3]. This makes PONV one of the most prevalent post-operational complaints [4].

Predicted risk factors for PONV can be classified into patient, anesthesia, and surgery related factors; the most important patient-related factors are female gender, below 50 years of age, history of motion sickness, and non-smoker status. However, there are many important surgery-related factors to consider. For example, strabismus and laparoscopic surgery are associated with the highest incidence rates of PONV [9]. Another study revealed that patients who underwent laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) experienced higher incidences of PONV compared to other surgeries, which they explained by an increased vagal impulse by the pneumoperitoneum [6]. Furthermore, prolonged duration of surgery (>30 mins) is also associated with a 60% increase in the risk of PONV [4]. Anesthetic factors that are also important to note include the specific drugs used for inducing anesthesia. For example, nitrous oxide, inhalational anesthetic agents, opioids, and neostigmine contribute to an increased risk of PONV [4].

A simple scoring system is essential for evaluating PONV risk factors. Effective identification of high-risk patients and using multimodal treatments can significantly reduce PONV and post-discharge nausea and vomiting (PDNV) [12]. The simplified Apfel score is used for assessing patients' risk of PONV, and it includes four main factors: previous history of motion sickness or PONV, postoperative use of opioids, non-smoking status, and female gender. Each one of these risk factors elevate the incidence of PONV by about 20% (one fifth). The total score helps predict the likelihood of PONV, higher scores indicate higher risk of PONV incidence [8]. However, it is important to note that while these scoring systems are useful, they are not absolute predictors, and individual responses to anesthesia and surgery can vary.

Usually, PONV either resolves on its own or is treated without sequelae. However, sometimes, it may require unanticipated hospital admission and may delay recovery room discharge. In addition, vomiting or retching can result in major and life-threatening complications like wound dehiscence, esophageal rupture, aspiration, dehydration, increased intracranial pressure, and pneumothorax [6].

Prompt management is crucial for PONV, traditional antiemetics for PONV include anticholinergics (scopolamine), phenothiazines (promethazine), antihistamines (diphenhydramine), butyrophenones

(droperidol) and benzamide (Metoclopramide). Despite the risks associated with PONV, a guaranteed solution has yet to be found. The physiology of nausea and vomiting involves multiple neurotransmitter pathways. Therefore, antiemetic drugs have been developed that are effective against 5-HT₃, D₂, NK₁, H₁, and mACh receptors. However, no antiemetic can reduce the incidence of PONV to zero. In fact, only 20–30% of the patients will respond to any currently available antiemetic [7].

Aim

The motivation behind this study lies in the absence of prior investigations on PONV prevention specifically within the Kurdistan region of Iraq. Our aim is to contribute some valuable insights to the medical community by collecting information from local patients, enhancing our ability to predict and treat PONV more accurately. More specifically, our aim is to provide valuable insights into PONV by studying local patients undergoing laparoscopic surgery, focusing on cholecystectomy situated in Kurdistan, our research seeks to refine care standards for these patients and contribute to improved perioperative practices in our local healthcare setting.

Methodology

Method

This study was performed in Azadi Teaching Hospital in the city of Duhok, KRI. Informed and written consent was obtained from all of the participants. The research was performed in accordance with the principles of the College of Health Sciences and was approved by the Ethics Committee of Duhok University and the Duhok Directorate General Health on March 27th, 2024 (approval number: 27032024-2-3). Accordingly, the researcher was given the right to publish the results of the study.

Cases were collected among the adult age group (17 years old and over) who received general anesthesia while undergoing laparoscopic surgery (mainly laparoscopic cholecystectomy). Patients were free to refuse their participation in this study. All personal information obtained from the participants has been kept confidential. The data that has been recorded includes patient risk factors, surgical risk factors, and anesthetic drugs used for induction and maintenance of general anesthesia. Recorded patient risk factors include Gender, Weight, Height, BMI, History of previous general anesthesia and/or PONV, History of previous motion sickness, and Smoking history. The anesthetic agents used for the induction of anesthesia (including the inhalational drugs) were all recorded. These mainly consisted of Propofol, Ketamine, Midazolam, Fentanyl, And the Inhalational drugs included Isoflurane or Sevoflurane. Additionally, the use of antiemetic drugs (Metoclopramide) and the duration of the operation were also recorded. Contact

numbers were taken to communicate with patients to follow up on the incidence of PONV, 48 hours after surgery.

Study Design

The following study is a case-control study that included 79 cases. As previously mentioned, the sample was entirely made up of patients receiving general anesthesia while undergoing laparoscopic surgery. The patients were randomly divided into two groups: Half of our patients received Metoclopramide intraoperatively (the intervention group). In contrast, the other half did not receive Metoclopramide (the control group) to observe differences in the incidence of PONV between the two groups. Only patients with a PONV risk score of >2 were included.

Data Analysis

The data was collected, managed, and analyzed using the SPSS software Package (IBM SPSS Statistics 20). Descriptive analysis (frequency, percent, and central tendency) of uni-variant variables was performed to understand the data better. The Chi-square tests were used to compare the proportion of cases of the outcome (nausea and vomiting) and the independent variables. A p-value of < 0.05 is assigned to be significant for the differences between the variables.

The **Shapiro-Wilk Test** was used for assessing normalcy; significant results indicated a non-normal distribution.

The **Mann-Whitney U test** is a relatively popular non-parametric method used to determine if there are significant differences in a scale or ordinal dependent variable between two independent groups. It serves as the nonparametric counterpart to the independent samples t-test. This test evaluates the mean ranks of scores in each Group to calculate the U statistic, which is then used to determine the p-value, indicating the significance level. A significant result from this test implies that the two groups have consistently different scores on the dependent variable. The test assumes that observations are independent and that the dependent variable is measured at a scale or ordinal level [10].

Binry Logistic Regression is another statistical method. It is useful in examining the relationship between a single dichotomous dependent (outcome) variable and one or more independent (predictor) variables. This analysis aims to estimate the probability of a case being a member of one Group or the other by using the independent variables [11].

Results

Medical History and Anesthetic Drugs Received During Operation

Table 1 shows that out of 79 females studied for PONV, 24 (30.38%) had a history of motion sickness, 27 (34.18%) had a history of PONV, 41 (51.90%) had a history of receiving general anesthesia, and none of

them were smokers. Furthermore, the results on the anesthetic drugs they received intraoperatively indicate that 77 (97.47%) received Propofol, 5 (6.33%) received ketamine, 76 (96.20%) received fentanyl, 75 (94.94%) received isoflurane, and 9 (11.39 %) received sevoflurane.

Table 1: Frequency and Percent for Medical History and Anesthetic Drugs Received During Operation

Variable	n	%
History of motion sickness	24	30.38
History of Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting	27	34.18
History of receiving general anaesthesia	41	51.90
No History of Smoking	79	100.00
Received Propofol	77	97.47
Received Ketamine	5	6.33
No Received Thiopental	79	100.00
Received Fentanyl	76	96.20
Received Isoflurane	75	94.94
Received Sevoflurane	9	11.39
Total	79	100

Note: Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Study Group, Obesity, and Outcomes

Table 2 shows that out of 79 patients, 40 (50.63%) received Metoclopramide, and 39 (49.37%) were included in the control group. Furthermore, 34 (43.04%) were obese (>= 30 kg sqm), and 22 (27.85%) experienced PONV.

Table 2: Frequency and Percent of Study Group, Obesity, and Outcomes

Variable	n	%
Group		
Metoclopramide	40	50.63
Control	39	49.37
Obesity (>=30 kg sqm)	34	43.04
Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting	22	27.85
Nausea	19	24.05
Retching	6	7.59
Vomiting	4	5.06
Total	79	100.0

Note: Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting (PONV) Risk Score

Table 3 summarizes the PONV risk scores. Results show a mean (sd) of 2.48 (0.62).

Table 3: Summary Statistics for Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score

Variable	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score	79	2.48	0.62

Descriptive Statistics for Age, Weight, Height, BMI, Nausea and Vomiting Duration, Operation Duration, and Nausea and Vomiting Onset

Table 4 summarizes the data obtained about age, weight, height, BMI, nausea and vomiting duration, operation duration, and nausea and vomiting onset (hours). The mean (sd) of age was 38.49 (12.27) years, 73.11 (14.45) for weight in kg, 1.58 (0,05) for height in meters, 29.24 (5.91) BMI, 13.67 (19.64) hours for duration of nausea and vomiting, 0.89 (0.21) hours duration of the operations, and within 15.85 (19.42) hours onset of nausea and vomiting.

Table 4: Summary Statistics for Age, Weight, Height, BMI, Nausea and Vomiting Duration, Operation Duration, and Nausea and Vomiting Onset (hours)

Variable	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Age (year)	79	38.49	12.27
Weight kg	79	73.11	14.45
Height (m)	79	1.58	0.05
BMI (kg sqm)	79	29.24	5.91
Nausea and vomiting Duration (hr.)	21	13.67	19.64
Operation Duration (hr.)	78	0.89	0.21
Nausea and vomiting onset (hr.)	22	15.85	19.42

Post-Operative Nausea and Vomiting

Based on an alpha value of 0.05, the results of the Chi-square test were not significant, $\chi^2(1) = 0.00$, $p = 0.944$, suggesting that Study Group variable and Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting could be independent of one another. Table 5 presents the results of the Chi-square test.

Table 5: Group Variable and Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting

Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting					
Group	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
Metoclopramide	11[27.5]	29[72.5]	0.00	1	0.944
Control	11[28.2]	28[71.8]			
Total	22 [27.8]	57 [72.2]			

The results of the Chi-square test were not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $\chi^2(1) = 0.52$, $p = 0.472$, suggesting that history of motion sickness and PONV could be independent of one another.

The results of the above test were not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $\chi^2(1) = 1.72$, $p = 0.189$,

suggesting that a history of PONV and PONV could be independent of one another.

The Chi-square test results were not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $\chi^2(1) = 0.07$, $p = 0.788$, suggesting that Obesity and PONV could be independent of one another. Table 6 presents the results of the Chi-square test.

Table 6: History of Motion Sickness, History of Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting and Obesity and Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting

Post-Operative Nausea and Vomiting					
	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
History of motion sickness	8 [33.3]	16 [66.7]	0.52	1	0.472
History of Post-Operative Nausea and Vomiting	10[37.0]	17[63.0]	1.72	1	0.189
Obese (≥ 30 kg sqm)	10[29.4]	24[70.6]	0.07	1	0.788

The Chi-square test results were not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $\chi^2(1) = 0.01$, $p = 0.914$, suggesting that a history of receiving general

anesthesia and study groups could be independent of one another. Table 7 presents the results of the Chi-square test.

Table 7: History of Receiving General Anesthesia and Study Group

Group					
History of receiving general anaesthesia	Metoclopramide n (%)	Control n (%)	χ^2	df	p
Yes	21[51.2]	20[48.8]	0.01	1	0.914
No	19[50.0]	19[50.0]			
Total	40 [50.6]	39 [49.4]			

Anesthetic drugs and PONV

The results of the Fisher exact test were not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $p = 1.000$, suggesting that Propofol use and PONV could be independent of one another. Table 8 presents the results of the Fisher's exact test.

The results of the Fisher exact test were not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $OR = 0.00$, $p = 0.315$, suggesting that Ketamine and Anesthetic drugs and PONV could be independent of one another. Table 9 presents the results of the Fisher's exact test.

Table 8: Propofol and Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting

Propofol			
Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	p
Yes	22[100.0]	0[0.0]	1.000
No	55[96.5]	2[3.5]	

Table 9: Ketamine and Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting

Ketamine				
Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	OR	p
Yes	0[0.0]	22[100.0]	0.00	0.315
No	5[8.8]	52[91.2]		

The results of the Fisher exact test were not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $p = 0.572$, suggesting that Isoflurane and PONV could be independent of one

another. Table 10 presents the results of the Fisher's exact test.

Table 10: Isoflurane and Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting

Isoflurane			
Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting	Yes n (%)	No n (%)	p
Yes	22[100]	0[0.0]	0.572
No	53[93.0]	4[7.0]	

PONV Risk Score

In order to determine whether the distribution of PONV Risk Score was normal, a Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted. Based on an alpha of 0.05, the following variables had significantly non-normal distributions: PONV Risk Score ($W = 0.70$, $p < 0.001$). The results are presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Shapiro-Wilk Test Results for Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score

Variable	W	p
Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score	0.70	< 0.001

PONV Risk Score and the Group Levels

A two-tailed Mann-Whitney two-sample rank-sum test was conducted to examine whether there were significant differences in PONV Risk Scores between the group levels. The two-tailed Mann-Whitney U test result was insignificant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $U = 798.5$, $z = -0.21$, $p = 0.835$. The mean rank for the Metoclopramide Group was 40.46 and the mean rank for the control group was 39.53. This suggests that the distribution of the PONV Risk Scores for the Metoclopramide Group ($Mdn = 2.00$) was not significantly different from that of the PONV Risk Scores for the Control ($Mdn = 2.00$) category. Table 12 presents the result of the two-tailed Mann-Whitney U test. Figure 1 presents a boxplot of the ranks of Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score by Group.

Table 12: Two-Tailed Mann-Whitney Test for Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score and the levels of Group

Variable	Metoclopramide		Control				
	Mean Rank	<i>n</i>	Mean Rank	<i>n</i>	<i>U</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score	40.46	40	39.53	39	798.50	-0.21	0.835

Figure 1: Ranks of Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score by Group

Figure 2: Ranks of Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score by Obesity

Table 13: Two-Tailed Mann-Whitney Test for Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score by Obesity

Variable	Obese (>=30 kg sqm)		Not Obese				
	Mean Rank	<i>n</i>	Mean Rank	<i>n</i>	<i>U</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p</i>
Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score	39.82	34	40.13	45	759.00	-0.07	0.946

Based on an alpha value of 0.05, the two-tailed Mann-Whitney U test results were insignificant. $U = 759$, $z = -0.07$, $p = 0.946$. The mean rank for the Obese Group (≥ 30 kg sqm) was 39.82 and the mean rank for the Not Obese Group was 40.13. This suggests that the distribution of PONV Risk Score for the Obese Group (≥ 30 kg sqm) (Mdn = 2.00) was not significantly different from the distribution of PONV Risk Score for the Not Obese (Mdn = 2.00) Group. Table 13 presents the result of the two-tailed Mann-Whitney U test. Figure 2 presents a boxplot of the ranks of PONV Risk Score by Obesity.

Relationship between history of motion sickness, history of PONV, Group, Obesity, and PONV Risk Score and PONV

The model was evaluated based on an alpha of 0.05. The overall model was significant, $\chi^2(8) = 15.60$, $p = 0.008$, suggesting that history of motion sickness, history of PONV, Group, Obesity, and PONV Risk Score

had significant effects on the odds of the occurrence of PONV. The McFadden R-squared value for this model was 0.17. The effect of no history of motion sickness was insignificant, $B = -0.29$, $OR = 0.74$, $p = 0.661$, indicating that observing no history of motion sickness did not significantly affect the odds of observing PONV. The effect of the No category of History of PONV was not significant, $B = 0.54$, $OR = 1.72$, $p = 0.446$, indicating that observing the No category of History of PONV did not significantly affect the odds of observing the Yes category of History of PONV. The effect of the Control category of the Group was insignificant, $B = 0.08$, $OR = 1.09$, $p = 0.887$, indicating that observing the Control category of the Group did not significantly affect the odds of observing the Yes category of History of PONV. Furthermore, the effect of the Not Obese category of Obesity was also insignificant, $B = -0.38$, $OR = 0.68$, $p = 0.503$, indicating that observing the Not Obese category of Obesity did not have significantly affect the odds of

observing the Yes category of History of PONV. However, the effect of the PONV Risk Score was significant, $B = 1.83$, $OR = 6.25$, $p < 0.001$, indicating that a one-unit increase in the PONV Risk Score increased

the odds of observing the Yes category of PONV by approximately 525.06%. A summary of the results of the regression model can be found in Table 14.

Table 14: Logistic Regression Results with History of motion sickness, History of motion sickness, Group, Obesity, and Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score Predicting Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting

Variable	B	SE	χ^2	p	OR	95.00% CI
(Intercept)	-5.66	1.74	10.54	.001	-	-
History of motion sickness (No)	-0.29	0.67	0.19	.661	0.74	[0.20, 2.78]
History of Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting (No)	0.54	0.71	0.58	.446	1.72	[0.43, 6.97]
Group (Control)	0.08	0.58	0.02	.887	1.09	[0.35, 3.37]
Obesity (Not Obese)	-0.38	0.57	0.45	.503	0.68	[0.22, 2.08]
Post Operative Nausea and Vomiting Risk Score	1.83	0.55	11.16	< .001	6.25	[2.13, 18.32]
<i>Note.</i> $\chi^2(5) = 15.60$, $p = .008$, McFadden $R^2 = 0.17$.						

Discussion

According to the results of our study, which was performed on high-risk score patients, Metoclopramide is ineffective in preventing PONV in high-risk patients, which can be attributed to a variety of factors [15]. Firstly, Metoclopramide mainly improves gastrointestinal movement rather than directly targeting the pathways responsible for nausea and vomiting. This limited focus might explain why it does not work well for these symptoms after surgery. Also, people react differently to Metoclopramide. Factors like genetic variations, other medical issues, or taking different medications alongside Metoclopramide can affect how well it works for each person. Furthermore, over time, patients who regularly take Metoclopramide might find it less effective in controlling postoperative symptoms. This happens because their bodies get used to the medication, causing tolerance to build up. As a result, the therapeutic benefits of metoclopramide decrease, leading to decreased efficacy in preventing nausea and vomiting.

Opposite to some studies that reveal the effectiveness of Propofol in the prevention of PONV [16], in our study, Propofol was ineffective in preventing (PONV) due to its primary action as a sedative-hypnotic agent, lacking direct antiemetic properties, individual variability in patient response, and dependence on factors like surgery type and patient health.

The short duration of operations included, each lasting less than one hour, correlates with the short duration of exposure to inhalational anesthetic agents, which was expected to be associated with less incidence of PONV [17], even though the incidence of PONV was high. Moreover, our findings showed that factors such as previous PONV episodes and a history of motion sickness did not affect the incidence of PONV [18].

We discovered a notable association between our PONV risk score and the likelihood of PONV development. However, it's important to note the limitations of our study, including the relatively small sample size and the lack of control over postoperative steroid administration. Additionally, the uniform dosing of Metoclopramide without adjusting for individual patient weights may have influenced the observed PONV incidence. Overall, the multifactorial nature of Metoclopramide's ineffectiveness in preventing PONV underscores the importance of considering alternative treatment options that target the underlying causes of these symptoms more directly and comprehensively.

Conclusion & Recommendations

PONV is one of the most common complications following general anesthesia in the first 24-48 hours, which can lead to poor outcomes in patients' recovery and increase postoperative morbidity. As some studies might show that Metoclopramide can be effective in prevention of PONV [19]. We recommend that further studies should be done to improve preventing PONV among high-risk patients however based on current evidence it is advisable that Metoclopramide should not be used as a single drug for preventing PONV and it should be used in combination with other drugs for example Dexamethasone, Ondansetron etc.

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